

Title: Narrow electroluminescence linewidths for reduced non-radiative recombination in organic solar cells and near-infrared light-emitting diodes

Quan Liu^{1,2}, Sander Smeets^{1,2}, Sigurd Mertens^{1,2}, Yuxin Xia^{1,2}, Andrea Valencia^{1,2}, Jan D'Haen^{1,2}, Wouter Maes^{1,2}, and Koen Vandewal^{1,2*}*

¹UHasselt – Hasselt University, Institute for Materials Research (IMO-IMOMEC), Agoralaan 1, 3590, Diepenbeek, Belgium

²IMOMEC Division, IMEC, Wetenschapspark 1, 3590, Diepenbeek, Belgium

*Corresponding author E-mail: quan.liu@uhasselt.be, koen.vandewal@uhasselt.be

Keywords: non-radiative recombination loss; electroluminescence linewidth; near-infrared organic light-emitting diode; nonfullerene solar cell, low-molecular-weight polymer

SUMMARY

Minimization of non-radiative recombination losses is essential to transcend the efficiency of state-of-the-art organic solar cells (OSCs) and near-infrared (NIR) organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs). Indeed, reduced non-radiative processes will result in a high electroluminescence (EL) external quantum efficiency (EQE_{EL}) and low non-radiative voltage losses ($\Delta V_{\text{OC,nr}}$) for OSCs. Here, we study the EL properties of a set of polymer-small molecule blends and find a relationship between the EL emission linewidth, EQE_{EL} and $\Delta V_{\text{OC,nr}}$. Based on these findings, we reduce $\Delta V_{\text{OC,nr}}$ from the typical values around 250 mV down to an unprecedented value of 155 mV using a blend comprising a low-molecular-weight PM6 polymer donor and a highly emissive non-fullerene acceptor (Y16F). Importantly, the PM6:Y16F blend yields an EQE_{EL} (0.52%) among the best reported fluorescent NIR-OLEDs in the 900 nm range.. These findings clearly indicate the existence of organic material blends which combine both excellent photovoltaic and electroluminescent properties.

INTRODUCTION

The performance of current organic opto-electronic devices, especially in the near-infrared (NIR) region, is limited by strong non-radiative transition pathways governed by the so-called 'energy-gap law'¹. This severely restricts the number of emitters suitable for NIR organic light-emitting diodes (NIR-OLEDs), while for NIR-harvesting organic solar cells (OSCs), it results in higher non-radiative open-circuit voltage losses ($\Delta V_{OC,nr}$) as compared to those of inorganic or perovskite-based technologies, and thus lower power conversion efficiencies (PCEs). Voltage losses in OSCs are linked to the external quantum efficiency of electroluminescence (EQE_{EL}), measured when a forward bias is applied to the device^{2,3}.

$$\Delta V_{OC,nr} \approx -\frac{k_B T}{q} \ln(EQE_{EL}) \quad (1)$$

In order to bring the open-circuit voltage (V_{OC}) closer to the optical gap, the energy offset between either the highest occupied or lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (HOMO or LUMO, respectively) energy levels of the donor (D) or acceptor (A) molecules needs to be minimized, and the lower gap material in the blend should be highly emissive⁴. Following these design rules, recent new-emerging donor:non-fullerene acceptor (NFA) blends with low energy offset yield high-efficiency OSCs (over 15%) with EQE_{EL} values in the 0.001–0.05% range, leading to $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ on the order of 0.2–0.3 V^{5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15}. The low-gap component of these devices is the NFA and the energy of the interfacial charge-transfer (CT) states is very close that of the NFA local exciton (LE). As a result, the emission spectrum and absorption tails consist of contributions of CT, LE and CT-LE hybrid states, or mid-gap trap states¹⁶, which are, however, difficult to distinguish from each other^{17,18,19}. Moreover, their emission quantum yield, and thus resulting $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ for a given D-A combination has been shown to depend on the interfacial morphology^{9,20,21} and molecular packing behavior²², causing variations in $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ in the range of 50–300 mV, i.e. changes in EQE_{EL} within a factor of about 10–10⁵ according to equation (1). In order to increase the PCE of OSCs, but also to enable NIR-OLEDs, it is of great importance to understand the molecular and morphological sources for non-radiative recombination in these low energy offset D:A blends.

The non-radiative decay rate is related to molecular vibrations and electron-phonon coupling by the energy gap law and theoretical models predict that the same parameters affect the fine structure and shape of the low energy part of the emission spectrum²³. In this work, we explore this relation and study a set of efficient polymer-NFA blends with different energy level offsets and blend morphologies. We find that the blends with larger offsets or lower neat NFA emission quantum yields have a broader electroluminescence (EL) emission spectrum. We further observe a broadening when a more strongly aggregated blend morphology is achieved for a certain D:A combination. In general, we find the linewidth of the EL spectrum to correlate strongly with $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$.

Based on these findings and with the aim of reducing $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ to unprecedented values, we designed blend combinations with an aggregation-less morphology using low-molecular-weight fractions of the polymer PM6 (poly[(2,6-(4,8-bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl-3-fluoro)thiophen-2-yl)-benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene))-*alt*-(5,5-(1',3'-di-2-thienyl-5',7'-bis(2-ethylhexyl)benzo[1',2'-*c*:4',5'-*c'*]dithiophene-4,8-dione))]). This enables emission linewidths for the blends as narrow as the neat NFA materials and $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ values for the resulting OSCs down to 155 mV. These devices have their emission peak in the 850–950 nm range and reach EQE_{EL} values up to 0.52%, with a remarkably low onset voltage (5 mA/cm² at 1.2 V). This makes the NFAs currently used in the best OSCs among the best emitters in NIR-OLEDs, with record conversion efficiencies of electrical power to NIR optical power (PCE_{LED}) in the 900 nm range. These findings emphasize that a narrow emission linewidth, high EQE_{EL} , low $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ and low emission onset voltage are strongly related and that future research on NIR-OLEDs and OSCs should go hand in hand.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Electroluminescence properties of low energetic offset polymer: NFA blends

For this study, we carefully chose a set of polymer:NFA combinations consisting of two well-known polymers (PTB7-Th and PM6) and three NIR light-absorbing non-fullerene acceptors with similar optical gaps (E_{opt}), being FOIC²⁴, Y6⁷ and its derivative Y16F⁹. Their chemical structures are shown in **Figure 1a**, alongside the electronic energy levels (**Figure 1b**) measured by cyclic voltammetry (CV) under the same conditions for all materials. Note that the HOMO energy levels derived from CV measurements on films (see Section S2) are likely to be slightly altered in the blend films due to modified molecular packing or morphology as compared to neat materials. All devices were fabricated in an inverted architecture, namely glass/ITO/ZnO sol-gel/active layer/MoO₃/Ag. They comprise next to the D:A blends also neat NFA photoactive layers, all processed at room temperature, without thermal treatment from an additive-free chloroform solvent, unless mentioned otherwise. The processing conditions were not optimized for achieving the highest possible cell efficiency, but enabled an easy comparison within different blend systems. Also, note that the studied blends had negligible degradation when stored in a nitrogen-filled glovebox for several months (Table S2). All key parameters are summarized in **Table 1** and the details of the photovoltaic parameters, EQE_{PV} and EQE_{EL} are shown in Section 3 of the Supplemental Information.

We first consider the influence of the energy level offset on the photovoltaic and emission properties. PTB7-Th yields the largest HOMO energy offset with FOIC, and PTB7-Th:FOIC devices yield a V_{OC} of 0.74 V, which is approximately 0.1 V less than that of PM6:FOIC cells. In both devices, no clear CT absorption is visible in the sub-gap region of the sensitively measured photovoltaic external quantum efficiency (EQE_{PV}) spectra (Figure S5) and no obvious extra emission band is observed in the EL spectrum (**Figure 1c**), which at first sight resembles the emission spectrum of neat FOIC. The reduced V_{OC} in the case of PTB7-Th is therefore mainly due to increased $\Delta V_{\text{OC,nr}}$, in good agreement with the observation that the EQE_{EL} of PTB7-Th:FOIC is about two orders of magnitude lower than that of the PM6:FOIC device (see EQE_{EL} spectra in Figure S6). Such an increase in EQE_{EL} upon minimizing the

HOMO energetic offset has been previously observed and explained by a hybridization of the CT state with the emissive LE states²⁵, or a thermal equilibration between the LE and CT state¹⁹. Both mechanisms are expected to affect the spectral shape of the emission spectrum as compared to that of the neat material. Furthermore, the emission line shape of the devices is strongly affected by self-absorption and optical interference (see Figures S9 and S11b)^{26,27}. For a fair comparison, we therefore made sure to control the thickness of the photoactive layers to be ca. 100 nm and defined the emission linewidth based on the log scale spectra as shown in **Figures 1 c–e**: the difference between the photon energies where the value of the normalized emission spectrum reaches 5×10^{-3} (grey line in Figures 1c–e) is taken as a measure to indicate the width of the emission spectrum. Note that this measure ΔE_{5E-3} is much more affected by emission tail at lower energies (see Figures 1c and e) than for example the full width at half maximum, and gives the best correlation with $V_{OC, nr}$ of all the studied OSCs (Figure S10) and later shown in Figure 4d.

Going back to the EL spectra of PM6:FOIC and PTB7-Th:FOIC, shown in Figure 1c, we observe a much larger ΔE_{5E-3} in the case of PTB7-Th, which has the larger HOMO offset. A similar observation is made in **Figure 1d**, which shows a larger ΔE_{5E-3} for PM6:Y6 as compared to PM6:FOIC. The latter has 0.2 eV less HOMO offset and a higher EQE_{EL} , even though a device containing neat FOIC has a lower EQE_{EL} than for neat Y6 (see Table 1 and Figure S6). The PM6:Y16F based devices show the smallest ΔE_{5E-3} of the D:A combinations described so far, as well as the highest EQE_{EL} (Table 1). We attribute the lower ΔE_{5E-3} for the Y16F devices to the fact that the Y16F LE has a narrower emission linewidth than the Y6 LE. In fact, in devices comprising neat NFA active layers, Y16F has the highest EQE_{EL} (Table 1, Figure S6).

We now turn our attention to morphological and aggregation effects affecting the emission properties. It is known that aggregation in blends has an influence on the frontier orbital energy levels²⁸ and thus on the degree of LE/CT hybridization and/or the LE/CT population equilibrium, as well as the voltage losses. In **Figure 1e**, EL spectra of PM6:Y6 devices for various thermal annealing temperatures are shown. Clearly, ΔE_{5E-3} increases with increasing temperature. The device annealed at 200 °C is expected

to have the largest extend of polymer and NFA aggregation, and yields the broadest EL spectrum and the largest $\Delta V_{OC, nr}$, over 80 mV larger than for the as-cast film (Table 1). As will be shown in the next section, these thermal-induced nanomorphologies changes are confirmed by AFM measurements.

Strategy for reducing $\Delta V_{OC, nr}$ for low energetic offset PM6:NFA solar cells

Inspired by the observation that an increased D-A intermixing and reduced aggregation narrows the emission spectrum and increases EQE_{EL} , we have synthesized low molecular weight PM6 polymer batches with the aim of manipulating the interfacial energy landscape and non-radiative recombination rate. For this purpose, a dedicated droplet flow polymerization protocol was applied. Details on the synthesis procedure are given in Section S1 in the Supporting Information. To examine the degree of intramolecular packing of the PM6 polymer, we recorded temperature dependent absorption spectra of the various molecular weight fractions in chloroform solution. As shown in **Figure 2a**, the standard PM6 with a number-average molar mass (M_n) of 33 kDa exhibits a pronounced shoulder at 615 nm, which only slightly reduces as the temperature increases, indicating an intrinsically strong aggregation of the polymer chains in both solution and the solid state^{29,30}. For the PM6 batches with reduced M_n , a large decrease of such shoulder peak was observed together with a gradual blue shift in absorption and a decrease of intensity with increasing temperature, suggesting that the low- M_n polymers are very weakly aggregated in solution. This dependence of the aggregation state on M_n is hypothesized to result in PM6:NFA films with varying degrees of intermixing or aggregated nanomorphology, schematically shown in **Figure 2b**. Morphology studies for all PM6:NFA blend films support this picture: As shown in **Figures 2d-e** and Figures S8 (a-b and d-e), AFM height and phase images suggested an obvious phase separation with well-distributed fibre-like aggregation textures in the high- M_n blend systems. In contrast, such aggregation pattern was almost invisible or weakened in the low low- M_n blend systems, indicating a more D/A intermixed nanomorphology. Furthermore, when the high- M_n PM6:Y6 blend was subjected to 200°C thermal annealing, the aggregates become more clearly visible (**Figure 2c**). TEM images (**Figure 2f** and Figures S8c and f) further support these observations: The uniformly distributed flower-like phase separation (indicative of aggregate morphology³¹) in all high- M_n blends disappears or greatly reduces in their low- M_n counterparts.

Decreasing the M_n improves the V_{OC} in the three studied blend systems, with the measured J - V curves shown in **Figures 3a-c**. The increase in V_{OC} is largest for the PM6:Y6 blend, approximately 75 mV when going from an M_n of 33 kDa to 10 kDa. A further reduction in M_n does not significantly improve the V_{OC} . We note that such large V_{OC} enhancement does not originate from reduced surface recombination or trap-assisted recombination in the BHJ blend³² since negligible changes were observed in the blend surface roughness (AFM images in Figure 2 and Figure S8), and the slope of the semi-logarithmic plot of the V_{OC} against light intensity (Figure S15). We therefore attribute such enhancement to a reduction in HOMO energetic offset between PM6 and Y6 when low- M_n polymer was used (Figure 1b). Additionally, the well-intermixed blend morphology reduces polymer aggregation and further lowers the HOMO level^{33,34}. The reduced $\Delta V_{OC, nr}$ agrees well with the EQE_{EL} measurements (Figure S6), and EQE_{EL} values in the low- M_n polymer based cells reach similar values as those of devices fabricated with the respective neat NFA materials. Furthermore, narrower EL spectra, shown in **Figures 3d-f**, were measured for the low- M_n polymer devices and their linewidths are comparable with those of pure NFA based devices (Figure 4a). The narrowed EL line-shape indicates a suppressed non-radiative decay rate via molecular vibrations, as discussed later.

Even though the V_{OC} improves, the short-circuit current (J_{SC}) and fill factor (FF) are sacrificed, resulting in lower overall efficiencies for the lower- M_n blend systems. A summary of the molecular weight dependent photovoltaic performance is given in Figure S14. J_{SC} losses for the lower- M_n PM6:Y6 blends are associated with a decreased internal quantum efficiency (IQE, Figure S16). We mainly attribute this to a reduced exciton dissociation efficiency. The photoluminescence (PL) in NFA is approximately 30% less quenched in the lower- M_n blend film, as shown in Figure S17, which is consistent with a J_{SC} reduced from 25.4 to 19.2 mA/cm². The reduced FF correlates with a reduced hole mobility. By decreasing M_n from 33k to 10kDa in the PM6:Y6 blend, electron mobilities remain unchanged while hole mobilities were reduced by more than one order of magnitude (Figure S18).

To further improve OSCs, in particular, to surpass the 20% efficiency barrier, EQE_{EL} enhancement should be achieved simultaneously with high IQE and high FF. Previous work has shown that the trade-

off between IQE and energetic offsets for current low-bandgap NFA cells^{35,36} can be overcome by increasing the exciton lifetimes of the low-gap NFA materials¹⁹. Moreover, a well-designed blend morphology with high and balanced mobilities are essential to maintain high FF, as well.

Correlation between non-radiative recombination loss and EL linewidth

Summarizing all data from the experiments on low energy offset polymer:NFA blends described above, a correlation can be seen between $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ and ΔE_{5E-3} . This clearly indicates that in our quest for high-efficiency organic solar cells, we should focus on those D:A blends, and hence neat materials, with the narrowest emission spectra.

We propose two possible origins for this remarkable observation. Even though no distinct CT emission band is observed, the anticipated slightly lower energy of the CT states might introduce, in addition to neat NFA emission, some extra low-energy emission, hereby broadening the spectra. Since CT states are less emissive than the neat LE of the NFA, a lower EQE_{EL} is indeed expected³⁷. However, this does not explain why the different neat NFAs have different EQE_{EL} values. In fact, the EQE_{EL} of the neat NFA devices also correlates with ΔE_{5E-3} , as shown in **Figure 4a**, with Y16F having the smallest ΔE_{5E-3} and the best EQE_{EL} among the three studied NFA materials.

The lineshape of the emission spectrum can be related to the excited state energy E_S and high and low frequency reorganization energies, λ_H and λ_L respectively. The line shape of the spectral flux of emitted photons N_{ph} is given by equation 2²³.

$$N_{ph} \sim E^3 \sum_{n=0}^{+\infty} \frac{\exp(-S)S^n}{n!} \exp\left(-\frac{(E - E_S + \lambda_L + nE_h)^2}{4\lambda_L kT}\right) \quad (2)$$

where E_h is the vibronic spacing and $S = \lambda_H/E_h$ the Huang Rhys factor. The parameters in equation (2) also determine the non-radiative decay rate, which is proportional to the reduced emission spectrum (N_{ph}/E^3) evaluated at a photon energy E of 0²³.

Figure 34b shows calculated emission spectra for an E_S of 1.40 eV, which is close to the gap of all three studied NFA materials, a typical E_h of 0.15 eV and selected values for λ_H and λ_L . Low-finesse optical

cavity (ITO-Ag) effects, together with a significant increase in ITO reflection for wavelengths larger than 1000 nm (Figure S11a) make it difficult to perform an accurate fitting of the measured emission spectra with equation (2). We also note that the measured line-width of the EL spectra are narrower than that of steady photoluminescence (PL) spectra because the emission intensity enhances in the cavity resonance region, while being suppressed in the off-resonance region (Figure S13)²⁷. Furthermore, the simplicity of equation (2) might not accurately capture all physical effects responsible for the broadening of the emission spectrum. However, a comparison between the curves following equation (2) and the experimental curves shows that all main features of the emission spectra present in the simple model are also experimentally observed (Figures 4a-b). We can state that the width of the EL spectrum, as defined by ΔE_{5E-3} , correlates with the total reorganization energy, which in the case of the simple model in equation (2) is the sum $\lambda_L + \lambda_H$. This is shown in **Figure 4c**, showing a linear relationship between ΔE_{5E-3} determined for selected curves following equation (2) and the total reorganization energy.

In **Figure 4d**, $\Delta V_{OC, nr}$ of all the studied devices based on blends and pure NFAs is plotted as a function of ΔE_{5E-3} . The correlation between these two quantities implies that a smaller total reorganization energy results both in narrower emission spectra and smaller non-radiative losses. Furthermore, we have shown in the previous paragraph that organic solar cells with proper design can have an emission linewidth and EQE_{EL} very close to that of the pure NFA material. The aggregation-less polymer:NFA blends demonstrated in this study are examples of the latter.

Performance of polymer:NFA devices as near-infrared OLEDs

For the D:A combinations studied in this work, we have observed that the IQE is sacrificed when an OSC blend has the emission properties of the neat NFA material. Even though the V_{OC} is increased, this leads to a lower overall photovoltaic performance (Table S4). However, as the V_{OC} of the devices increases and approaches the radiative limit, the D:A blends are expected to be good LEDs, demonstrating a high EQE_{EL} . In fact, very recently, a bifunctional OLED-OPV device emitting around 700 nm was demonstrated using a wide-bandgap NFA blend, exhibiting 0.2% EQE_{EL} , as well as 26% PCE under indoor illumination conditions by a 1000 lux LED³⁸. This is a new type of organic opto-

electronic, which has not been extensively studied. New fundamental working mechanisms different from classical fluorescent OLEDs are however expected: Their emission is based on hybrid local and charge transfer states (HLCT). While not many studies have been performed on the exact working mechanism, exciton utilization efficiency values could break the spin-statistics limit of 25% since CT states and fluorescent excitons, as well as free charge carriers are all close in energy and can convert into each other.

While OLEDs with EQE_{EL} values reaching over 30% have been achieved in the visible spectral region^{39,40,41,42,43,44}, achieving high-performance devices has been proportionally more difficult with increasing design wavelength due to the energy gap law. The best reported NIR-OLEDs in the 900–950 nm range, based on triplet 5-(2-pyridyl)pyrimidinate Pt(II) complexes, do not have an EQE_{EL} larger than 2.1%⁴⁵. The PM6:Y16F system described above is actually among the best NIR-OLEDs within the spectral region beyond 900 nm based on fluorescent organic materials⁴⁶ (see Table S7), even though Y16F was designed as an OSC material and not specifically as a NIR-OLED material.

To further improve the light-emitting properties, we dispersed Y16F molecules into the small molecular weight PM6 ($M_n \approx 10$ kDa) host material at a lower concentration than in the OSC devices (1:1.2) to prevent exciton self-quenching in the blended emitting layer. Their thin-film absorption, steady PL and estimated PL quantum efficiencies are shown in Figure S19. The strongest EL intensity observed under the same injected current was from devices emitting at 890 nm in which a PM6:Y16F blend with a weight ratio of 3:1 was used, shown in **Figure 5a**. A blue-shift in the EL signal from the devices is seen as the Y16F concentration reduces, which we attribute to the diminished Y16F molecular aggregation in the blended films. **Figure 5b** shows EQE_{EL} as function of injected current density for the devices, with the highest EQE_{EL} achieved being 0.52%, which is two times larger than that of the neat Y16F device. We note that, in comparison with literature reported NIR-OLEDs with an emission peak maximum from 800 to 1,000 nm (see Table S7), our highest-performance NIR-OLED device outperforms most of the fluorescent OLEDs, with only few exceptions (**Figure 5c**), and approaches the

best-performing heavy-metal based phosphorescent NIR-OLEDs. In the optimized 3:1 NIR-OLED, we measured a V_{OC} as high as 0.98 V for an optical gap of 1.43 eV, resulting in a voltage loss of 0.46 V and a $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ below 0.14 V, which is in good agreement with the theoretically calculated value using equation S1 (see Section S3; detailed EQE_{PV} and photovoltaic parameters are shown in Section S7).

As compared to previously reported other types of NIR-OLED materials such as fluorescent host-guest systems, vacuum-processed phosphorescent metal-based complexes, or thermally activated delayed fluorescence (TADF) emitters, the design using polymer donor-acceptor organics allows for simple, cost-effective fabrication, heavy-metal-free, and lower onset voltages of emission^{47, 48}. This is beneficiary as it allows to achieve a high radiance at a lower voltage, thus resulting in a higher conversion efficiency of electrical power into optical power. The current density-voltage-radiance (J - V - L) characteristics of the PM6:Y16F OLED devices are shown in **Figure 5d**. All NIR-OLEDs fabricated feature low turn-on voltages of less than 1.0 V for a measurable photon output, although a slight increase was found when the Y16F concentration in the blend decreases. The high EQE_{EL} recorded in the lower concentration blend devices, taken together with the low driving voltages, result in a high PCE_{LED} . As shown in **Figure 5e**, the optimal device performs with a peak PCE as high as 0.66%, a nearly four-fold improvement over the values of recently reported best-performing phosphorescent NIR-OLEDs⁴⁵ ($EQE_{EL} \sim 2.1\%$, $PCE_{LED} \sim 0.16\%$) based on Pt(II) emitters with similar emission peak (see PCE_{LED} comparison in **Figure 5f**).

Conclusion

We have experimentally observed a correlation between EL linewidth, EL quantum efficiency and non-radiative voltage losses in several systems with low energetic offset between polymer donor and NFA acceptor wherein the emission spectra are dominated by the properties of the low-gap NFAs. The emission properties are varied by varying the HOMO energy level offset between the polymer and NFA, the emission quantum yield of the NFA and by tuning the blend morphology. Our observations show that in these systems, both the non-radiative decay rate and the EL linewidth are affected similarly by

molecular properties, being the reorganization energy and the possible presence of very weakly emitting CT states with an energy slightly below that of the local NFA exciton. Based on this, a reduced $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ was successfully achieved by using low-molecular-weight PM6 polymer with a designed aggregation-less blend morphology and minimized HOMO offset with the NFAs FOIC, Y6 and Y16F. The smaller $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ of OSCs thus corresponds to a narrower electroluminescence emission width, which is comparable with their pure NFA counterpart. Considering the low $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$, particularly in the PM6:Y16F blend, we further demonstrated solution-processable heavy metal-free OLEDs achieving electroluminescence in the 890–930 nm range by optimizing the Y16F concentration in the blend. The optimal $E_{QE,EL}$ is among the best reported fluorescent NIR-OLEDs that emit in the 900 nm range. Furthermore, when power efficiency is considered, we achieved a PCE_{LED} outperforming currently reported NIR-OLEDs in the wavelength range above 850 nm as a result of the low emission onset voltage. We therefore conclude that in order to reach increased efficiencies for both NIR-harvesting OSCs and NIR-OLEDs, novel low-gap organic semiconductors with narrow EL emission linewidths, indicative of low reorganization energies, are essential.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Materials and solution preparation. The polymer PM6 ($M_n \approx 33$ and 20 kDa) and the non-fullerene acceptors (Y6, Y16F and FOIC) were purchased from 1-material. PTB7-Th was purchased from Solaris Chem. Low- M_n PM6 polymer batches ($M_n \approx 10$ and 5 kDa) were synthesized at Hasselt University using a dedicated continuous droplet flow polymerization procedure⁴⁹. Experimental details are shown in Section 1 of the Supporting Information. All materials were used as received without further purification. The sol-gel ZnO precursor (0.45 M) was prepared by dissolving zinc acetate dehydrate (Aldrich, 99.9%, 0.5 g) and ethanolamine (Aldrich, 99.5%, 0.14 g) in 2-methoxyethanol (Acros Organics, 99.8%, 5 mL)⁵⁰. To complete the hydrolysis reaction, this solution was vigorously stirred at 60 °C for 2 h and then stirred at room temperature for 12 h in air. Solutions of PM6:NFA, PTB7-Th:FOIC and pure NFA at a total concentration of 11–16 mg/mL (donor/acceptor = 1:1.2 wt/wt in all the blends) were prepared in chloroform and stirred at 50 °C for 2 h in a N₂-filled glovebox before use.

Device fabrication. OSCs and NIR-OLEDs were fabricated using the same inverted device structure glass/ITO/ZnO/Active layer/MoO₃/Ag. We firstly spin-coated the ZnO precursor solution on pre-cleaned and UV-Ozone treated ITO (Biotain Crystal, 15 Ω sq⁻¹) substrates and it was annealed at 180 °C in air for 20 min to form a 30 nm electron-transporting layer. The prepared samples were then transferred into a N₂-filled glovebox for spin-coating the active layer with controlled thicknesses (90–100 nm) by adjusting the spin-casting rate. The blend thickness was monitored by a Bruker Veeco Dektak XT profilometer. Finally, the MoO₃ (10 nm) hole-transporting layer and the Ag (100 nm) electrode were sequentially deposited on the active layer through a shadow mask by thermal evaporation ($<5 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar) with an area of 0.06 cm². The freshly fabricated devices were encapsulated with glass slides using an UV-curable epoxy (DELO-LP655) in the glovebox and measured in air. *J-V* curves (forward scan with a step of 25 mV) were recorded using a Keithley 2400 Source Meter under AM1.5 1-sun illumination provided by a solar simulator (Newport 91195A) with an intensity equivalent to 100 mW cm⁻², which was calibrated with a Silicon reference cell. The EQE_{PV} spectrum for each cell was measured under chopped (135 Hz) monochromatic illumination from a Xe lamp (100 W, Newport) modulated by Cornerstone™ 130 Monochromator and an optical wheel chopper. The generated photocurrent from the solar cells was amplified with a Stanford Research System Model SR830 lock-in amplifier, and a calibrated Si photodiode with known spectral response was used as a reference.

FTPS-EQE and EQE_{EL} measurements. FTPS-EQE measurements were performed using a INVENIO R (Bruker Optics) with an external detector. A low-noise current amplifier was used to amplify the photocurrent generated under illumination of the devices, with the illumination light modulated by the Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR) setup. The EQE_{EL} was recorded with a home-built setup using a 100 mm² Hamamatsu silicon photodiode, which was placed directly in front of the device with a distance of 12 mm. A Keithley 2400 source meter was used to supply voltage and record the injected current, and simultaneously another Keithley 2400 was used to measure the emitted photons from the device. The radiance of the OLEDs was estimated using the same EQE_{EL} setup and Lambertian emission was assumed. The thickness of the glass substrate was considered when calculating the solid angle.

Electroluminescence measurements. The EL emission spectra were recorded using an Andor spectrometer (Kymera 328i-D2-SIL) with an InGaAs array detector (DU490A-1.7), which was cooled to -60 °C. A 830 nm long-pass filter was used to exclude the presence of peaks originating from the second order of diffraction from the grating. The voltage bias was applied to devices with a Keithley 2400 external current/voltage source meter. The injected current was close to J_{SC} of OSC devices measured under AM1.5G illumination at 100 mW/cm², except the low EQE_{EL} PTB7-Th:FOIC and 200 °C annealed 33k_PM6:Y6 cells, in which the injected current is approximately 3 times the J_{SC} . We further provided the injection dependent EL spectra of PTB7-Th:FOIC and 200°C annealed 33k_PM6Y6 cells in Figure S12. That figure makes clear that the EL shape of the spectra remains unchanged when going from an injection current close to $1 \cdot J_{SC}$ (~1.6 mA) to $3 \cdot J_{SC}$ (~5 mA). The details of injection current density and applied voltages were also indicated in the Supplemental Information, see Table S5. The system was wavelength-calibrated by an argon lamp (HG-2, Ocean Optics) with a resolution better than 0.5 nm and irradiance-calibrated by a NIST (National Institute of Standards and Technology) calibrated light source (AvaLight-HAL-CAL-Mini, 300–2500 nm). For recovering the high-energy tail part of the EL spectra, a CCD silicon array detector (DU416A-LDC-DD) with an 590 nm long-pass filter was used (see Figure S9).

Morphology characterization. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed with a Tecnai G2 Spirit Twin. The TEM samples are identical to the active layers of the solar cells, spin-coated on glass/PEDOT:PSS substrates, subsequently floated off on a copper TEM grid (3.05 mm diameter, 400 mesh) in DI-water. Bright field TEM images were recorded with a magnification of 30 kx. Atomic force microscopy (AFM) measurements were performed with a JPK/Bruker Nanowizard 3 in tapping mode.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Q.L. acknowledges financial support from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie -Curie grant (agreement No. [882794](#)). K.V. and W.M. are grateful for project funding by the FWO (Ph.D. scholarship S.S.; projects G0D0118N, G0B2718N, G0D1521N, I006320N and GOH3816NAUHL) and the European Research Council (ERC, grant agreement 864625).

A.V acknowledges financial support from FWO Odysseus program under G0D0115N project. The authors also thank Huguette Penxten for the CV measurements, and professor Frank Renner for help with AFM measurements.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Q.L. performed the core of the experimental work; S.S synthesized low molecular weight PM6 polymers under the supervision of W.M.; S.M and Y.X. helped with EL, PL and FTPS-EQE measurements; A.V. performed AFM measurements and J. D. measured the TEM samples. Q.L. and K.V. wrote the manuscript with the assistance from all other authors.

DECLARATION OF INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Table 1. Summary of key parameters for the studied devices in this work.

Active material	E_g/q (V)	V_{OC} (V)	PCE (%)	EQE_{PV} max in NFA (%)	$E_g/q -$ V_{OC} (V)	$V_{OC,rad}$ (V)	Calc. $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ (V)	Exp. EQE_{EL}	Exp. $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$ (V)
33k_PM6:Y6	1.41	0.837	15.4	82	0.57	1.085	0.248	6.3E-5	0.250
33k_PM6:Y6 (150 °C)	1.39	0.805	15.2	85	0.58	1.071	0.266	2.6E-5	0.274
33k_PM6:Y6 (200 °C)	1.39	0.739	11.5	84	0.65	1.067	0.328	2.6E-6	0.333
10k_PM6:Y6	1.42	0.910	7.6	66	0.51	1.095	0.185	1.0E-3	0.177
Y6	1.39	0.902	0.07	—	0.49	—	—	1.5E-3	0.167
PTB7-Th:FOIC	1.38	0.737	11.3	81	0.65	1.062	0.325	4.5E-6	0.318
33k_PM6:FOIC	1.38	0.845	7.5	50.0	0.54	1.064	0.219	2.6E-4	0.213
10k_PM6:FOIC	1.39	0.870	3.9	27	0.52	1.071	0.201	7.1E-4	0.187
FOIC	1.37	0.872	0.15	—	0.50	—	—	1.0E-3	0.178
33k_PM6:Y16F	1.39	0.881	12.2	74	0.50	1.076	0.195	6.8E-4	0.188
10k_PM6:Y16F	1.39	0.922	5.2	49	0.47	1.080	0.158	2.5E-3	0.155
10k_PM6:Y16F (1.5:1)	1.41	0.953	2.23	30	0.46	1.099	0.146	3.6E-3	0.145
10k_PM6:Y16F (3:1)	1.43	0.980	1.05	16	0.45	1.120	0.140	5.0E-3	0.137
Y16F	1.37	0.889	0.03	—	0.49	—	—	2.6E-3	0.154

The optical gap (E_{opt}) is determined from the intersection of the normalized EQE_{PV} and EL spectra (Figure S7). The detailed photovoltaic parameters and EQE_{EL} of the devices are summarized in Table S4 and Figure S6, respectively. Radiative open-circuit voltages ($V_{OC,rad}$) were calculated from the FTPS- EQE_{PV} spectra (Figure S5) shown in Section S3. Calculated non-radiative recombination (Calc. $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$) values of the devices are determined by $V_{OC,rad} - V_{OC}^{22}$ and experimental values (Exp. $\Delta V_{OC,nr}$) are directly obtained from $\Delta V_{OC,nr} = \frac{kT}{q} \ln\left(\frac{1}{EQE_{EL}}\right)$.

Figure 1. low LE-CT energetic offset active material systems and their electroluminescence properties. (a) Molecular structures of the donor polymers and low- E_{opt} NFAs used in this study. (b) Energy levels of the materials (experimental details in section S2 in the Supplemental Information). (c) Normalized EL spectra of devices based on PTB7-Th:FOIC and 33k_PM6:FOIC blends. (d) Normalized EL spectra of 33k_PM6:Y6, Y16F and FOIC based solar cells. (e) Evolution of the EL spectra for 33k_PM6:Y6 devices with varying pre-annealing temperatures for 15 minutes on the active layers.

Figure 2. Construction of blend films with reduced aggregates and morphology characterization.

(a) Temperature dependent absorption spectra for different molecular weight batches of PM6 in chloroform solution. The dotted spectra stand for thin films. (b) Schematic drawing of the possible nanomorphology evolution in the PM6:NFA blends. At the top, high- M_n polymer chains induce large aggregates for both PM6 and the NFA, while at the bottom, the low- M_n polymer increases the intermixing of the two phases by reducing their self-aggregation. (c)-(e) Atomic force microscope (AFM) images of the 200°C thermally annealed 33kPM6:Y6, as-cast 33kPM6:Y6 and 10kPM6:Y6 blend films on ITO/ZnO substrates, respectively. Top: height images; Bottom: phase images. (f) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of the as-cast 33kPM6:Y6 (top) and 10kPM6:Y6 (bottom) blend films.

Figure 3. Low-molecular-weight blends with less-aggregation morphology minimize non-radiative recombination losses. (a)–(c) *J*-*V* curves of solar cells based on high-*M_n* and low-*M_n* PM6:NFA blends measured under AM1.5G sunlight at 100mW/cm². (d)–(f) Corresponding normalized EL spectra (eV).

Figure 4. Correlation of the emission spectrum width with EQE_{EL}. (a) Measured EL spectra of neat NFA based devices with similar thickness as the blends used for solar cells. (b) Computed EL spectra with a set of reorganization energies $E_s = 1.40$ eV, $E_h = 0.15$ eV, $\lambda_H = 0.4$ – 0.9 eV and $\lambda_L = 0.5$ – 1.3 eV. (c) Plot of the calculated spectrum width as a function of reorganization energies. The solid line presents the best linear fit for the computed data. (d) Correlation between the emission spectrum width (see details in Table S4) and non-radiative recombination voltage losses of all the studied devices. Relevant EQE_{EL} values are indicated as grey solid lines. The black solid line presents the best linear fit of the experimental data.

Figure 5. Performance of near-infrared OLED devices. (a) Electroluminescence spectra of 10k_PM6:Y16F based OLED devices with different weight ratios (injected current = 1 mA). (b) EQE_{EL} of the devices plotted against the injected current density. (c) EQE_{EL} plotted against literature values with reported EL emission peaks ranging from 800 to 1000 nm. (d) J - V - R curves, showing turn-on voltages are less than 0.9 V. (e) PCE of devices with applied voltage bias. $PCE_{LED} = EQE_{EL} \times hv/eV$, wherein hv is the energy of the emitted photons, e is the elementary charge and V is the voltage applied to the devices. (f) PCE comparison with NIR-OLEDs reported in literature.

REFERENCES

- ¹ Caspar, J. V., and Meyer, T. J. (1983). Application of the energy gap law to nonradiative, excited-state decay. *J. Phys. Chem.* *87*, 952–957.
- ² Rau, U. (2007). Reciprocity relation between photovoltaic quantum efficiency and electroluminescent emission of solar cells. *Phys. Rev. B* *76*, 085303.
- ³ Benduhn, J., Tvingstedt, K., Piersimoni, F., Ullbrich, S., Fan, Y., Tropiano, M., McGarry, K.A., Zeika, O., Riede, M.K., Douglas, C.J., et al. (2017). Intrinsic non-radiative voltage losses in fullerene-based organic solar cells. *Nat. Energy* *2*, 17053.
- ⁴ Qian, D., Zheng, Z., Yao, H., Tress, W., Hopper, T.R., Chen, S., Li, S., Liu, J., Chen, S., Zhang, J., et al. (2018). Design rules for minimizing voltage losses in high-efficiency organic solar cells. *Nat. Mater.* *17*, 703–709.
- ⁵ Armin, A., Li, W., Sandberg, O.J., Xiao, Z., Ding, L., Nelson, J., Neher, D., Vandewal, K., Shoaee, S., Wang, T., et al. (2021). A History and Perspective of Non-Fullerene Electron Acceptors for Organic Solar Cells. *Adv. Energy Mater.* *11*, 2003570.
- ⁶ Li, C., Zhou, J., Song, J., Xu, J., Zhang, H., Zhang, X., Guo, J., Zhu, L., Wei, D., Han, G., et al. (2021). Non-fullerene acceptors with branched side chains and improved molecular packing to exceed 18% efficiency in organic solar cells. *Nat. Energy*. 10.1038/s41560-021-00820-x
- ⁷ Yuan, J., Zhang, Y., Zhou, L., Zhang, G., Yip, H.-L., Lau, T.-K., Lu, X., Zhu, C., Peng, H., Johnson, P.A., et al. (2019). Single-Junction Organic Solar Cell with over 15% Efficiency Using Fused-Ring Acceptor with Electron-Deficient Core. *Joule* *3*, 1140–1151.
- ⁸ Jiang, K., Wei, Q., Lai, J.Y.L., Peng, Z., Kim, H.K., Yuan, J., Ye, L., Ade, H., Zou, Y., and Yan, H. (2019). Alkyl Chain Tuning of Small Molecule Acceptors for Efficient Organic Solar Cells. *Joule* *3*, 3020–3033.
- ⁹ Liu, S., Yuan, J., Deng, W., Luo, M., Xie, Y., Liang, Q., Zou, Y., He, Z., Wu, H., and Cao, Y. (2020). High-efficiency organic solar cells with low non-radiative recombination loss and low energetic disorder. *Nat. Photonics* *14*, 300–305.
- ¹⁰ Cui, Y., Yao, H., Zhang, J., Zhang, T., Wang, Y., Hong, L., Xian, K., Xu, B., Zhang, S., Peng, J., et al. (2019). Over 16% efficiency organic photovoltaic cells enabled by a chlorinated acceptor with increased open-circuit voltages. *Nat. Commun.* *10*, 2515.
- ¹¹ Yu, R., Yao, H., Cui, Y., Hong, L., He, C., and Hou, J. (2019). Improved Charge Transport and Reduced Nonradiative Energy Loss Enable Over 16% Efficiency in Ternary Polymer Solar Cells. *Adv. Mater.* *31*, 1902302.
- ¹² Wang, Y., Wang, Y., Zhu, L., Liu, H., Fang, J., Guo, X., Liu, F., Tang, Z., Zhang, M., and Li, Y. (2020). A novel wide-bandgap small molecule donor for high efficiency all-small-molecule organic solar cells with small non-radiative energy losses. *Energy Environ. Sci.* *13*, 1309–1317.

- ¹³ Cui, Y., Yao, H., Zhang, J., Xian, K., Zhang, T., Hong, L., Wang, Y., Xu, Y., Ma, K., An, C., et al. (2020). Single-Junction Organic Photovoltaic Cells with Approaching 18% Efficiency. *Adv. Mater.* *32*, 1908205.
- ¹⁴ Zhan, L., Li, S., Xia, X., Li, Y., Lu, X., Zuo, L., Shi, M., and Chen, H. (2021). Layer-by-Layer Processed Ternary Organic Photovoltaics with Efficiency over 18%. *Adv. Mater.* *33*, 2007231.
- ¹⁵ Yan, T., Ge, J., Lei, T., Zhang, W., Song, W., Fanady, B., Zhang, D., Chen, S., Peng, R., and Ge, Z. (2019). 16.55% efficiency ternary organic solar cells enabled by incorporating a small molecular donor. *J. Mater. Chem. A* *7*, 25894–25899.
- ¹⁶ Zarrabi, N., Sandberg, O.J., Zeiske, S., Li, W., Riley, D.B., Meredith, P., and Armin, A. (2020). Charge-generating mid-gap trap states define the thermodynamic limit of organic photovoltaic devices. *Nat. Commun.* *11*, 5567.
- ¹⁷ Eisner, F.D., Azzouzi, M., Fei, Z., Hou, X., Anthopoulos, T.D., Dennis, T.J.S., Heeney, M., and Nelson, J. (2019). Hybridization of Local Exciton and Charge-Transfer States Reduces Nonradiative Voltage Losses in Organic Solar Cells. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* *141*, 6362–6374.
- ¹⁸ Xu, Y., Yao, H., Ma, L., Hong, L., Li, J., Liao, Q., Zu, Y., Wang, J., Gao, M., Ye, L., et al. (2020). Tuning the Hybridization of Local Exciton and Charge-Transfer States in Highly Efficient Organic Photovoltaic Cells. *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* *59*, 9004–9010.
- ¹⁹ Classen, A., Chochos, C.L., Lüer, L., Gregoriou, V.G., Wortmann, J., Osvet, A., Forberich, K., McCulloch, I., Heumüller, T., and Brabec, C.J. (2020). The role of exciton lifetime for charge generation in organic solar cells at negligible energy-level offsets. *Nat. Energy* *5*, 711–719.
- ²⁰ Ran, N.A., Roland, S., Love, J.A., Savikhin, V., Takacs, C.J., Fu, Y.-T., Li, H., Coropceanu, V., Liu, X., Brédas, J.-L., et al. (2017). Impact of interfacial molecular orientation on radiative recombination and charge generation efficiency. *Nat. Commun.* *8*, 79.
- ²¹ Jain, N., Chandrasekaran, N., Sadhanala, A., Friend, R.H., McNeill, C.R., and Kabra, D. (2017). Interfacial disorder in efficient polymer solar cells: The impact of donor molecular structure and solvent additives. *J. Mater. Chem. A* *5*, 24749–24757.
- ²² Rosenthal, K.D., Hughes, M.P., Luginbuhl, B.R., Ran, N.A., Karki, A., Ko, S., Hu, H., Wang, M., Ade, H., and Nguyen, T. (2019). Quantifying and Understanding Voltage Losses Due to Nonradiative Recombination in Bulk Heterojunction Organic Solar Cells with Low Energetic Offsets. *Adv. Energy Mater.* *9*, 1901077.
- ²³ Azzouzi, M., Yan, J., Kirchartz, T., Liu, K., Wang, J., Wu, H., and Nelson, J. (2018). Nonradiative Energy Losses in Bulk-Heterojunction Organic Photovoltaics. *Phys. Rev. X* *8*, 031055.
- ²⁴ Li, T., Dai, S., Ke, Z., Yang, L., Wang, J., Yan, C., Ma, W., and Zhan, X. (2018). Fused Tris(thienothiophene)-Based Electron Acceptor with Strong Near-Infrared Absorption for High-Performance As-Cast Solar Cells. *Adv. Mater.* *30*, 1705969.

- ²⁵Bixon, M., Jortner, J., and Verhoeven, J.W. (1994). Lifetimes for Radiative Charge Recombination in Donor-Acceptor Molecules. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* *116*, 7349–7355.
- ²⁶ Armin, A., Zarrabi, N., Sandberg, O.J., Kaiser, C., Zeiske, S., Li, W., and Meredith, P. (2020). Limitations of Charge Transfer State Parameterization Using Photovoltaic External Quantum Efficiency. *Adv. Energy Mater.* *10*, 2001828.
- ²⁷ List, M., Sarkar, T., Perkhun, P., Ackermann, J., Luo, C., and Würfel, U. (2018). Correct determination of charge transfer state energy from luminescence spectra in organic solar cells. *Nat. Commun.* *9*, 3631.
- ²⁸ Vandewal, K., Gadisa, A., Oosterbaan, W.D., Bertho, S., Banishoeib, F., Van Severen, I., Lutsen, L., Cleij, T.J., Vanderzande, D., and Manca, J. V. (2008). The Relation Between Open-Circuit Voltage and the Onset of Photocurrent Generation by Charge-Transfer Absorption in Polymer: Fullerene Bulk Heterojunction Solar Cells. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* *18*, 2064–2070.
- ²⁹ Zhang, M., Guo, X., Ma, W., Ade, H., and Hou, J. (2015). A Large-Bandgap Conjugated Polymer for Versatile Photovoltaic Applications with High Performance. *Adv. Mater.* *27*, 4655–4660.
- ³⁰ Qian, D., Ye, L., Zhang, M., Liang, Y., Li, L., Huang, Y., Guo, X., Zhang, S., Tan, Z., and Hou, J. (2012). Design, Application, and Morphology Study of a New Photovoltaic Polymer with Strong Aggregation in Solution State. *Macromolecules* *45*, 9611–9617.
- ³¹ Cho, Y., Kumari, T., Jeong, S., Lee, S.M., Jeong, M., Lee, B., Oh, J., Zhang, Y., Huang, B., Chen, L., et al. (2020). Guest-oriented non-fullerene acceptors for ternary organic solar cells with over 16.0% and 22.7% efficiencies under one-sun and indoor light. *Nano Energy* *75*, 104896.
- ³² Cowan, S.R., Roy, A., and Heeger, A.J. (2010). Recombination in polymer-fullerene bulk heterojunction solar cells. *Phys. Rev. B* *82*, 245207.
- ³³ Sweetnam, S., Prasanna, R., Burke, T.M., Bartelt, J.A., and McGehee, M.D. (2016). How the Energetic Landscape in the Mixed Phase of Organic Bulk Heterojunction Solar Cells Evolves with Fullerene Content. *J. Phys. Chem. C* *120*, 6427–6434.
- ³⁴ Sweetnam, S., Graham, K.R., Ngongang Ndjawa, G.O., Heumüller, T., Bartelt, J.A., Burke, T.M., Li, W., You, W., Amassian, A., and McGehee, M.D. (2014). Characterization of the Polymer Energy Landscape in Polymer:Fullerene Bulk Heterojunctions with Pure and Mixed Phases. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* *136*, 14078–14088.
- ³⁵ Xie, Y., Wang, W., Huang, W., Lin, F., Li, T., Liu, S., Zhan, X., Liang, Y., Gao, C., Wu, H., et al. (2019). Assessing the energy offset at the electron donor/acceptor interface in organic solar cells through radiative efficiency measurements. *Energy Environ. Sci.* *12*, 3556–3566.
- ³⁶ Karuthedath, S., Gorenflot, J., Firdaus, Y., Chaturvedi, N., De Castro, C.S.P., Harrison, G.T., Khan, J.I., Markina, A., Balawi, A.H., Peña, T.A. Dela, et al. (2021). Intrinsic efficiency limits in low-bandgap non-fullerene acceptor organic solar cells. *Nat. Mater.* *20*, 378–384.

- ³⁷ Perdigón-Toro, L., Phuong, L.Q., Zeiske, S., Vandewal, K., Armin, A., Shoaee, S., and Neher, D. (2021). Excitons Dominate the Emission from PM6:Y6 Solar Cells, but This Does Not Help the Open-Circuit Voltage of the Device. *ACS Energy Lett.* *6*, 557–564.
- ³⁸ Xu, Y., Cui, Y., Yao, H., Zhang, T., Zhang, J., Ma, L., Wang, J., Wei, Z., and Hou, J. (2021). A New Conjugated Polymer that Enables the Integration of Photovoltaic and Light-Emitting Functions in One Device. *Adv. Mater.* 2101090.
- ³⁹ Jeon, S.O., Lee, K.H., Kim, J.S., Ihn, S.-G., Chung, Y.S., Kim, J.W., Lee, H., Kim, S., Choi, H., and Lee, J.Y. (2021). High-efficiency, long-lifetime deep-blue organic light-emitting diodes. *Nat. Photonics* *15*, 208–215.
- ⁴⁰ Chan, C.-Y., Tanaka, M., Lee, Y.-T., Wong, Y.-W., Nakanotani, H., Hatakeyama, T., and Adachi, C. (2021). Stable pure-blue hyperfluorescence organic light-emitting diodes with high-efficiency and narrow emission. *Nat. Photonics* *15*, 203–207.
- ⁴¹ Wu, T.-L., Huang, M.-J., Lin, C.-C., Huang, P.-Y., Chou, T.-Y., Chen-Cheng, R.-W., Lin, H.-W., Liu, R.-S., and Cheng, C.-H. (2018). Diboron compound-based organic light-emitting diodes with high efficiency and reduced efficiency roll-off. *Nat. Photonics* *12*, 235–240.
- ⁴² Kondo, Y., Yoshiura, K., Kitera, S., Nishi, H., Oda, S., Gotoh, H., Sasada, Y., Yanai, M., and Hatakeyama, T. (2019). Narrowband deep-blue organic light-emitting diode featuring an organoboron-based emitter. *Nat. Photonics* *13*, 678–682.
- ⁴³ Ahn, D.H., Kim, S.W., Lee, H., Ko, I.J., Karthik, D., Lee, J.Y., and Kwon, J.H. (2019). Highly efficient blue thermally activated delayed fluorescence emitters based on symmetrical and rigid oxygen-bridged boron acceptors. *Nat. Photonics* *13*, 540–546.
- ⁴⁴ Lee, Y.H., Park, S., Oh, J., Woo, S.-J., Kumar, A., Kim, J.-J., Jung, J., Yoo, S., and Lee, M.H. (2018). High-Efficiency Sky Blue to Ultradeep Blue Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescent Diodes Based on Ortho -Carbazole-Appended Triarylboron Emitters: Above 32% External Quantum Efficiency in Blue Devices. *Adv. Opt. Mater.* *6*, 1800385.
- ⁴⁵ Wei, Y.-C., Wang, S.F., Hu, Y., Liao, L.-S., Chen, D.-G., Chang, K.-H., Wang, C.-W., Liu, S.-H., Chan, W.-H., Liao, J.-L., et al. (2020). Overcoming the energy gap law in near-infrared OLEDs by exciton–vibration decoupling. *Nat. Photonics* *14*, 570–577.
- ⁴⁶ Zampetti, A., Minotto, A., and Cacialli, F. (2019). Near-Infrared (NIR) Organic Light-Emitting Diodes (OLEDs): Challenges and Opportunities. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* *29*, 1807623.
- ⁴⁷ Ullbrich, S., Benduhn, J., Jia, X., Nikolis, V.C., Tvingstedt, K., Piersimoni, F., Roland, S., Liu, Y., Wu, J., Fischer, A., et al. (2019). Emissive and charge-generating donor-acceptor interfaces for organic optoelectronics with low voltage losses. *Nat. Mater.* *18*, 459–464.
- ⁴⁸ Chen, D., Xie, G., Cai, X., Liu, M., Cao, Y., and Su, S.-J. (2016). Fluorescent Organic Planar pn Heterojunction Light-Emitting Diodes with Simplified Structure, Extremely Low Driving Voltage, and High Efficiency. *Adv. Mater.* *28*, 239–244.

⁴⁹ Beckers, O., Gielen, S., Verstraeten, F., Verstappen, P., Lutsen, L., Vandewal, K., and Maes, W. (2020). Continuous Droplet Flow Synthesis of a Near-Infrared Responsive Push–Pull Copolymer toward Large Scale Implementation of Organic Photodetectors. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* 2, 4373–4378.

⁵⁰ Liu, Q., Gerling, L.G., Bernal-Texca, F., Toudert, J., Li, T., Zhan, X., and Martorell, J. (2020). Light Harvesting at Oblique Incidence Decoupled from Transmission in Organic Solar Cells Exhibiting 9.8% Efficiency and 50% Visible Light Transparency. *Adv. Energy Mater.* 10, 1904196.

Table of Contents

Section S1: Synthesis and characterization of low molecular weight PM6	2
Section S2. Energy level measurements	5
Section S3. Photovoltaic performance, EQE_{PV}, EQE_{EL} and morphology of the studied solar cells.....	6
Section S4. Accurate determination of the emission spectrum linewidth	13
Section S5. Molecular weigh dependent photovoltaic performance of PM6:Y6 solar cells.....	17
Section S6. Absorption, steady PL and PLQY of 10k_PM6:Y16F emitters.....	21
Section S7. Energy loss analysis for 10k_PM6:Y16F OLED devices as solar cells	22

Section S1: Synthesis and characterization of low molecular weight PM6

Materials and methods

All reagents and chemicals were obtained from commercial sources and used without further purification. (4,8-Bis(5-(2-ethylhexyl)-4-fluorothiophen-2-yl)benzo[1,2-*b*:4,5-*b'*]dithiophene-2,6-diyl)-bis(trimethylstannane) (BDT-F) and 1,3-bis(5-bromothiophen-2-yl)-5,7-bis(2-ethylhexyl)-4*H*,8*H*-benzo[1,2-*c*:4,5-*c'*]dithiophene-4,8-dione (BDD) were purchased from 1-material. Polymer molar mass distributions were estimated by size exclusion chromatography at 160 °C on an Agilent 1260 Infinity II high-temperature GPC system using a PL-GEL 10 μm MIXED-B column with 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene as the eluent and using polystyrene internal standards. Preparative (recycling) size exclusion chromatography (prep-SEC) was performed on a JAI LC-9110 NEXT system equipped with JAIGEL 1*H*, 2*H*, and 3*H* columns (eluent CHCl_3 , flow rate 3.5 mL min^{-1}).

General droplet flow polymerization procedure

Flow experiments were conducted on a home-made continuous flow system.¹ The droplet flow setup consisted of two Chemyx Fusion 100 syringe pumps, a home-made Teflon droplet generator and a planar PFA tubular reactor of 1.13 mL (0.75 mm in diameter), held in place by a stainless steel oil bath. Before and after every injection, the system was flushed with freshly degassed chlorobenzene and with degassed Fomblin L 06/6 perfluoropolyether (PFPE) upfront. Furthermore, a temperature equilibration of 30 min was performed before each injection. When not in use, the systems were stored under chlorobenzene. The reactor and setup (**Figure S1**) used for these experiments were recently reported.¹

Figure S1. Representation of the droplet-flow setup.¹

All reagents were dissolved in degassed chlorobenzene and loaded into syringes under nitrogen atmosphere. Degassed Fomblin L 06/6 PFPE was also loaded into a gas-tight 25 mL SGE syringe under nitrogen atmosphere. Two gas-tight SGE syringes were used for the monomers and the catalyst-ligand solution. The monomer syringe was loaded with BDT-F (1 equiv, 154 mg/mL) and BDD (1 equiv, 125 mg/mL), and the catalyst syringe with Pd₂(dba)₃ (0.03 equiv, 4.5 mg/mL) and tri-*o*-tolylphosphine (0.12 equiv, 6 mg/mL). Syringe pumps were used to inject all solutions simultaneously into the pre-heated reactor at the desired flow speed. In all experiments, a 5:1 flow rate ratio was used between the PFPE and chlorobenzene streams. After collection in a round-bottom flask, the polymers were washed 3 times with (degassed) low-boiling Galden HT55 PFPE to get rid of the high-boiling Fomblin L 06/6 PFPE. The PFPE fluids were recycled afterwards. The Galden HT55 PFPE was removed from the polymer solution *in vacuo*. Diethylammonium diethyldithiocarbamate (0.6 equiv) was added in chlorobenzene. The mixture was stirred at 100 °C for 1 h, concentrated *in vacuo* and the polymer was precipitated in an excess of methanol. Thereafter, the polymer was purified by successive Soxhlet extractions with methanol, acetone, *n*-hexane, dichloromethane, and chloroform, respectively. The polymer was collected with chloroform, precipitated once again in methanol, and finally collected by vacuum filtration and dried under high vacuum (80–95% yield).

Plug flow residence time determination

To estimate the reaction time needed to obtain a specific molar mass polymer sample, small plugs of 0.1 mL of the reaction mixture were injected into the preheated reactor, propelled by degassed Fomblin L 06/6 PFPE and using set flow speeds. All other reaction conditions and the polymer work-up were kept identical as described in the general procedure, except for the absence of Soxhlet extractions. The obtained molar masses were plotted against the residence time to provide a rough estimate of the reaction time needed to obtain a specific molar mass sample (see **Figure S2**). The residence times used to synthesize 5k and 10k PM6 were 1.8 and 2.5 min, respectively.

Figure S2. Residence times plotted versus the obtained molecular mass from the plug flow experiment.

Table S1. GPC data of the different PM6 polymer batches.

PM6	M_n (g mol ⁻¹)	M_w (g mol ⁻¹)	M_z (g mol ⁻¹)	PDI
33k (1-material)	33066	76240	132425	2.31
20k (1-material)	20256	36079	59832	1.79
10k (synthesized)	10658	20617	37099	1.93
5k (synthesized)	4867	9547	16412	1.96

Table S2. Durability data of the studied blends.

	Measured on 24/07/2020				Re-measured on 12/11/2020			
	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)
PTB7-Th:FOIC	11.09	67.3	22.48	0.733	10.78	68.4	21.24	0.741
	Measured on 06/06/2020				Re-measured on 12/11/2020			
	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)
33kPM6:Y16F	11.96	60.4	22.42	0.883	11.88	62.9	21.45	0.880
	Measured on 13/04/2020				Re-measured on 14/05/2020			
	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)
33kPM6:Y6	15.34	71.3	26.01	0.827	15.22	71.3	25.75	0.829
	Measured on 15/01/2021				Re-measured on 14/05/2021			
	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)	PCE (%)	FF (%)	J_{sc} (mA/cm ²)	V_{oc} (V)
33kPM6:FOIC	7.35	55.5	15.87	0.835	7.46	56.3	15.77	0.840

Note: All the blend films were as-cast, and the photovoltaic parameters were averaged from 4-6 cells.

Section S2. Energy level measurements

Cyclic voltammetry (CV) was performed with an Eco Chemie Autolab PGSTAT 30 potentiostat/galvanostat using a three-electrode microcell with a platinum working electrode, a platinum wire counter electrode, and a Ag/AgNO₃ wire reference electrode (silver wire dipped in a solution of 0.01 M AgNO₃ and 0.1 M NBu₄PF₆ in anhydrous acetonitrile). All the solutions were deaerated by bubbling through nitrogen gas for a few minutes prior to the electrochemical measurements. The reference electrode was calibrated against ferrocene/ferrocenium (Fc/Fc⁺) as the internal standard. The onset potential of the Fc/Fc⁺ redox couple was found to be 0.07 eV relative to the Ag/AgNO₃ reference electrode in our measurement system, and the energy level of Fc/Fc⁺ was assumed to be at -4.98 eV under vacuum. Samples were prepared by dip-coating the platinum working electrode in the respective polymer or NFA solution in chloroform. Thus, the energy of the highest occupied molecular orbital (HOMO) was calculated from the equation $E_{\text{HOMO}} = -(E_{\text{onset (ox)}} - E_{\text{onset (ferrocene)}} + 4.98)$ eV, and the energy of the lowest unoccupied molecular orbital (LUMO) was calculated from $E_{\text{LUMO}} = E_{\text{g (opt)}} + E_{\text{HOMO}}$.

Figure S3. Cyclic voltammograms for the polymers (up) and NFA materials (bottom). The onset of oxidation is determined via the intersection of the linear fits (dashed lines) in the regime before the onset of oxidation and in the first oxidation regime. The resulting energy levels are list in **Table S3**.

Table S3. HOMO and LUMO energies of the donor and acceptor materials.

Material	HOMO (eV)	LUMO (eV)	E_g (opt) (eV)
33k_PM6	-5.48	-3.63	1.85
10k_PM6	-5.54	-3.68	1.86
PTB7-Th	-5.36	-3.75	1.61
Y6	-5.73	-4.37	1.36
Y16F	-5.66	-4.32	1.33
FOIC	-5.51	-4.19	1.32

Section S3. Photovoltaic performance, EQE_{PV}, EQE_{EL} and morphology of the studied solar cells

Table S4. Summary of the photovoltaic performance for the studied OSCs using standard polymers under AM 1.5G solar illumination at 100 mW/cm².

Active material	J_{SC} (J_{EQE}) ^{a)} [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{OC} [V]	FF [%]	PCE ^{b)} [%]
33k_PM6:Y6	25.4 ± 0.2 (24.5)	0.835 ± 0.001	71.6 ± 0.4	15.22 ± 0.16 (15.40)
33k_PM6:Y6 (150 °C)	26.7 ± 0.4 (25.4)	0.802 ± 0.002	69.6 ± 1.2	14.88 ± 0.32 (15.25)
33k_PM6:Y6 (200 °C)	26.2 ± 0.4 (25.1)	0.739 ± 0.002	61.3 ± 0.7	11.87 ± 0.11 (12.02)
10k_PM6:Y6	19.9 ± 0.4 (19.2)	0.908 ± 0.002	40.9 ± 1.2	7.38 ± 0.30 (7.69)
PCE10:FOIC	22.7 ± 0.3 (22.3)	0.738 ± 0.002	67.0 ± 1.0	11.25 ± 0.26 (11.31)
33k_PM6:FOIC	15.6 ± 0.4 (15.3)	0.841 ± 0.002	55.8 ± 0.5	7.31 ± 0.21 (7.55)
10k_PM6:FOIC	9.1 ± 0.2 (8.9)	0.865 ± 0.003	45.9 ± 0.4	3.63 ± 0.67 (3.88)
33k_PM6:Y16F	22.8 ± 0.5 (22.3)	0.878 ± 0.002	58.9 ± 0.9	11.76 ± 0.39 (12.20)
10k_PM6:Y16F	14.3 ± 0.2 (13.7)	0.920 ± 0.002	38.5 ± 0.3	5.06 ± 0.10 (5.17)

a) Calculated from EQE spectra. b) The average values and standard deviations are obtained from over 6 devices and the best PCE values are shown in the parentheses.

Figure S4. EQE_{PV} spectra of the devices based on different polymer: NFA systems.

Radiative V_{OC} calculation

$V_{OC,rad}$ is the theoretical maximum for the V_{OC} when all non-radiative pathways are eliminated. From the measured sensitive EQE_{PV} spectra, shown in **Figure S3**, $V_{OC,rad}$ can be calculated using the following equation:²

$$V_{OC,rad} = \frac{k_B T}{q} \ln \left(\frac{\int EQE(E) \times \phi_{AM1.5}(E) dE}{\int EQE(E) \times \phi_{BB}(E) dE} + 1 \right) \quad (S1)$$

where k is the Boltzmann-constant, T is the absolute room temperature, and $\phi_{BB}(E)$ is the black-body spectrum at 300 K, given by

$$\phi_{BB}(E) = \frac{2\pi E^2}{h^3 c^2} \frac{1}{(\exp(E/kT) - 1)} \quad (S2)$$

where h is Planck's constant and c is the speed of light in vacuum.

Figure S5. FTPS- EQE_{PV} spectra of the devices based on different bulk heterojunction systems. Tails in the low energy part are recovered from the EL spectra. The alignment of EL and FTPS-EQE was used to calculate $V_{OC,rad}$.

Figure S6. Electroluminescence quantum efficiency (EQE_{EL}) of the solar cells based on polymer:NFA blend films and neat NFA films.

Figure S7. Optical gap determined by the crossing point between the normalized EL (red) and EQE_{PV} (blue) spectra³.

EL and EQE_{PV} spectra are normalized to the highest energy peak and lowest energy peak, respectively.

Figure S8. AFM and TEM images. (a), (b), (d) and (e) AFM height and phase images of PM6:Y16F(FOIC) blend films with different molecular weight on glass/ITO/ZnO substrates. Top: height image; Bottom: phase images. (c) and (f) TEM images.

Section S4. Accurate determination of the emission spectrum linewidth

Figure S9. EL spectra and determination of emission width. (a) The accurate EL emission spectrum was determined by both Si (700–900 nm) and InGaAs (900–1600 nm) detectors. (b) The resulting EL spectrum is in semi-logarithmic plot and the emission width is calculated by $E_H - E_L$, which are the intersections of the reference line of $5E-3$ and the EL spectrum in the high and low-energy regions, respectively.

Figure S10. Comparison of correlation between the emission width and $V_{OC, nr}$ of all the studied devices when different values ($5E-3$, $5E-2$, and $5E-1$) that the normalized EL spectrum reaches were taken.

Figure S11. Cavity effect on EL spectra. (a) Transmission and reflectance of the glass/ITO substrate. A strong increase in reflectance is observed for wavelengths longer than 1000 nm, results in significant optical interference. (b) Active layer thickness dependent EL spectra, which are affected by optical interference (weak ITO-Ag cavity effect) in the low-energy region. When the blend thickness increases, cavity resonance shifts to lower energy, and thus broader EL emission is observed. Therefore, for a fair comparison between the different material systems, all blend thicknesses should be kept similar (~100 nm).

Figure S12. Bias-dependent EL spectra of devices. (a) PTB7-Th:FOIC; (b) 200°C annealed 33k_PM6:Y6. Negligible change was observed in the EL spectra when the injected current density increases to equivalent 3 times of J_{sc} measured under AM1.5G illumination at 100 mW/cm².

Figure S13. Comparison between normalized EL and PL. (a)-(c) 33kPM6:Y6 blend thickness dependent EL and PL. (d)-(f) NFA neat material based EL and PL. The blend and NFA-only films were prepared with the same experimental condition for PL (glass/ active layer) and EL (ITO/ZnO/ active layer/MoO₃/Ag) measurements.

Table S5. Summary of the calculated emission linewidths (ΔE_{5E-3}) and EL measurement details for the studied devices.

Device	E_L (eV)	E_H (eV)	$E_H - E_L$ (eV)	EXP.EQE _{EL}	Exp. $\Delta V_{oc, nr}$ (V)	Injected current (mA)	Applied voltage (V)
Y6	0.934	1.536	0.602	1.54E-03	0.167	0.30	1.07
33k_PM6:Y6-as cast	0.881	1.557	0.676	6.25E-05	0.250	1.64	0.91
33k_PM6:Y6-150°C	0.851	1.555	0.704	2.55E-05	0.274	1.62	0.87
33k_PM6:Y6-200°C	0.779	1.558	0.779	2.58E-06	0.333	5.00	0.88
10k_PM6:Y6-as cast	0.935	1.557	0.622	1.02E-03	0.177	1.11	1.05
FOIC	0.918	1.524	0.606	1.02E-03	0.178	0.30	1.03
33k_PM6:FOIC-as cast	0.910	1.530	0.620	2.64E-04	0.213	0.70	0.95
10k_PM6:FOIC-as cast	0.942	1.535	0.593	7.10E-04	0.187	0.56	0.95
PTB7-Th:FOIC	0.790	1.542	0.752	4.10E-06	0.321	4.70	0.90
Y16F	0.942	1.514	0.572	2.58E-03	0.154	0.30	1.09
33k_PM6:Y16F-as cast	0.940	1.530	0.590	6.84E-04	0.188	1.40	1.10
10k_PM6:Y16F	0.971	1.53	0.559	2.50E-03	0.155	0.85	1.07

Section S5. Molecular weight dependent photovoltaic performance of PM6:Y6 solar cells

Figure S14. Photovoltaic performance of PM6:Y6 devices based on different molecular weights of PM6. (a) V_{oc} . (b) EQE_{EL} . (c) J_{sc} (IQE was determined in Figure S16). (d) FF and PCE.

Figure S15. Semi-log plot of the measured V_{oc} as a function of light intensity for PM6:Y6 devices based on 10 and 33 kDa polymers.

Figure S16. IQE determination of PM6:Y6 devices with different M_n . (a) Molecular weight (M_n) dependent optical constants for PM6:Y6 blends. (b–e) Estimation of the internal quantum efficiency (IQE) for PM6:Y6 solar cells. The IQE was determined by scaling the transfer matrix method (TMM) calculated absorption in the active layer of a device to match the magnitude of the experimental EQE.

Figure S17. Steady-state photoluminescence (PL) spectra of neat films (dashed lines) and different M_n PM6:Y6 blends (solid lines) after (a) PM6 donor and (b) Y6 acceptor excitation. The percentage PL quenching (PLQ) indicated in the legend. For the excitation of 450 nm laser and 638 nm laser, 515nm and 715 nm longpass filters were used, respectively. Each of PL spectra was normalized to the absorbed photons at laser wavelengths (450 nm or 638 nm) determined from the UV-Vis-NIR absorption spectra of the thin films.

Figure S18. J - V curves of hole-only (left) and electron-only (right) devices measured under dark. The mobilities were extracted by fitting the dark J - V characteristics of single charge carrier devices using the SCLC Mott-Gurney model⁴, which is described by the equation:

$$J_{SCLC} = \frac{9}{8} \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \mu \frac{(V - V_{bi})^2}{L^3} \exp\left(\beta \sqrt{\frac{V - V_{bi}}{L}}\right),$$

where ϵ_0 is the permittivity of free space, ϵ_r is the relative permittivity of the active material (assumed to be 3.5), V_{bi} is the built-in voltage (determined to be 0.1 V for both single carrier devices), μ_0 the zero-field mobility, L is the thickness of the active layer, V is the bias voltage and β the field activation factor. The solid lines present the best fit of the experimental data using the equation. The electron- and hole-only device structure was ITO/ZnO/ blend films/LiF/Al and ITO/PEDOT:PSS/ blend films/MoO₃/Ag, respectively.

Section S6. Absorption, steady PL and PLQY of 10k_PM6:Y16F emitters

Figure S19. Absorption, PL and PLQY of 10k_PM6:Y16F emitters. (a) Absorption spectra and (b) steady photoluminescence (PL) spectra of 10k_PM6:Y16F blend films on glass substrates. Excitation source $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 638$ nm, with a 715 nm longpass filter. (c)-(e) Measured PL count spectra of laser ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 638$ nm) and glass/10k_PM6:Y16F samples for calculating PL quantum yields (PLQY). The PLQE was measured in an integrating sphere with two steps: (1) no sample is placed in the integrating sphere and only measure the excitation source intensity, (3) the sample is placed in the integrating sphere in the path of the excitation source. Then, the PLQY was calculated by dividing the integration of net emission (800-1100 nm) by the net photon absorption (515-800 nm).

Section S7. Energy loss analysis for 10k_PM6:Y16F OLED devices as solar cells

Figure S20. Energy loss analysis for 10k_PM6:Y16F devices. (a) and (b) are normal EQE (nm) and FTPS-EQE (eV) spectra for 10k_PM6:Y16F based devices with various weigh ratios, respectively. (c)–(e) are the optical gaps for such blend based devices determined by the intersection of the normalized EL and EQE spectra.

Table S6. Photovoltaic parameters for the 10k_PM6:Y16F devices with different D:A ratio under AM 1.5G solar illumination at 100 mW/cm².

10k_PM6:Y16F (wt/wt)	$J_{sc} (J_{EQE})^a$ [mA cm ⁻²]	V_{oc} [V]	FF [%]	PCE ^a [%]
1:1.2	14.3 ± 0.2 (13.7)	0.920 ± 0.002	38.5 ± 0.3	5.06 ± 0.1 (5.17)
1.5:1	8.5 ± 0.2 (8.2)	0.951 ± 0.002	26.5 ± 0.2	2.15 ± 0.1 (2.23)
3:1	4.7 ± 0.1 (4.5)	0.978 ± 0.002	22.1 ± 0.3	1.01 ± 0.05 (1.05)
4:1	2.8 ± 0.2 (3.7)	0.937 ± 0.003	21.8 ± 0.3	0.58 ± 0.04 (0.62)

a) Average values and standard deviations are obtained from over 6 devices and the best PCE values are shown in parentheses.

Table S7. Overview of published NIR-OLEDs to date with emission peaks ranging from 780 to 1000 nm.

	NIR EL peak (nm)	EQE _{EL} (%)	V (V) @ EQE _{EL}	PCE (%) @ EQE _{EL}	Ref.
Phosphorescent	800	1.2	6.0	0.31	5
Fluorescent	802	0.43	5.5	0.12	6
Phosphorescent	803	9.6	8.0	1.85	7
Phosphorescent	814	1.5	10.0	0.23	8
Phosphorescent	848	2.1	7.0	0.44	9
Fluorescent	840	1.15	3.5	0.49	10
Fluorescent	841	1.2	15.0	0.12	11
Fluorescent	864	0.20	5.5	0.05	6
Fluorescent	880	0.13	15.0	0.01	12
Phosphorescent	896	2.0	8.0	0.35	13
Phosphorescent	890	2.1	18	0.16	14
Fluorescent	895	0.09	20.0	0.01	15
Fluorescent	895	0.091	8.0	0.02	16
Fluorescent	900	0.8	10.4	0.13	17
Phosphorescent	900	1.36	17.0	0.11	15
Fluorescent	904	0.015	4.0	0.01	18
Phosphorescent	930	1.73	18.0	0.13	14
Fluorescent	930	0.004	16.0	0.0003	12
Fluorescent	939	0.006	55.0	0.0001	15
Fluorescent	960	0.02	10.0	0.0026	16
Fluorescent	970	0.05	1.1	0.0581	19
Fluorescent	990	0.018	40.0	0.0006	15
10k_PM6:Y16F(3:1,wt)	890	0.52	1.10	0.66	this work
10k_PM6:Y16F(1.5:1,wt)	903	0.38	1.00	0.52	this work
10k_PM6:Y16F(1:1.2,wt)	923	0.29	0.92	0.42	this work

References

- ¹ Beckers, O., Gielen, S., Verstraeten, F., Verstappen, P., Lutsen, L., Vandewal, K., and Maes, W. (2020). Continuous Droplet Flow Synthesis of a Near-Infrared Responsive Push–Pull Copolymer toward Large Scale Implementation of Organic Photodetectors. *ACS Appl. Polym. Mater.* *2*, 4373–4378.
- ² Vandewal, K., Tvingstedt, K., Gadisa, A., Inganäs, O., and Manca, J. V. (2009). On the origin of the open-circuit voltage of polymer–fullerene solar cells. *Nat. Mater.* *8*, 904–909.
- ³ Vandewal, K., Benduhn, J., and Nikolis, V.C. (2018). How to determine optical gaps and voltage losses in organic photovoltaic materials. *Sustain. Energy Fuels* *2*, 538–544.
- ⁴ Azimi, H., Senes, A., Scharber, M.C., Hingerl, K., and Brabec, C.J. (2011). Charge Transport and Recombination in Low-Bandgap Bulk Heterojunction Solar Cell using Bis-adduct Fullerene. *Adv. Energy Mater.* *1*, 1162–1168.
- ⁵ Nisic, F., Colombo, A., Dragonetti, C., Roberto, D., Valore, A., Malicka, J.M., Cocchi, M., Freeman, G.R., and Williams, J.A.G. (2014). Platinum(ii) complexes with cyclometallated 5- π -delocalized-donor-1,3-di(2-pyridyl)benzene ligands as efficient phosphors for NIR-OLEDs. *J. Mater. Chem. C* *2*, 1791.
- ⁶ Du, X., Qi, J., Zhang, Z., Ma, D., and Wang, Z.Y. (2012). Efficient Non-doped Near Infrared Organic Light-Emitting Devices Based on Fluorophores with Aggregation-Induced Emission Enhancement. *Chem. Mater.* *24*, 2178–2185.
- ⁷ Wang, S.F., Yuan, Y., Wei, Y., Chan, W., Fu, L., Su, B., Chen, I., Chou, K., Chen, P., Hsu, H., et al. (2020). Highly Efficient Near-Infrared Electroluminescence up to 800 nm Using Platinum(II) Phosphors. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* *30*, 2002173.
- ⁸ Lee, T.-C., Hung, J.-Y., Chi, Y., Cheng, Y.-M., Lee, G.-H., Chou, P.-T., Chen, C.-C., Chang, C.-H., and Wu, C.-C. (2009). Rational Design of Charge-Neutral, Near-Infrared-Emitting Osmium(II) Complexes and OLED Fabrication. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* *19*, 2639–2647.
- ⁹ Huang, L., Park, C.D., Fleetham, T., and Li, J. (2016). Platinum (II) azatetrabenzoporphyrins for near-infrared organic light emitting diodes. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* *109*, 233302.
- ¹⁰ Minotto, A., Murto, P., Genene, Z., Zampetti, A., Carnicella, G., Mammo, W., Andersson, M.R., Wang, E., and Cacialli, F. (2018). Efficient Near-Infrared Electroluminescence at 840 nm with “Metal-Free” Small-Molecule:Polymer Blends. *Adv. Mater.* *30*, 1706584.
- ¹¹ Shahalizad, A., Malinge, A., Hu, L., Laflamme, G., Haeberlé, L., Myers, D.M., Mao, J., Skene, W.G., and Kéna-Cohen, S. (2021). Efficient Solution-Processed Hyperfluorescent OLEDs with Spectrally Narrow Emission at 840 nm. *Adv. Funct. Mater.* *31*, 2007119.
- ¹² Murto, P., Minotto, A., Zampetti, A., Xu, X., Andersson, M.R., Cacialli, F., and Wang, E. (2016). Triazolobenzothiadiazole-Based Copolymers for Polymer Light-Emitting Diodes: Pure Near-Infrared Emission via Optimized Energy and Charge Transfer. *Adv. Opt. Mater.* *4*, 2068–2076.
- ¹³ Sommer, J.R., Farley, R.T., Graham, K.R., Yang, Y., Reynolds, J.R., Xue, J., and Schanze, K.S. (2009). Efficient Near-Infrared Polymer and Organic Light-Emitting Diodes Based on Electrophosphorescence from (Tetraphenyltetranaphtho[2,3]porphyrin)platinum(II). *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* *1*, 274–278.

-
- ¹⁴ Wei, Y.-C., Wang, S.F., Hu, Y., Liao, L.-S., Chen, D.-G., Chang, K.-H., Wang, C.-W., Liu, S.-H., Chan, W.-H., Liao, J.-L., et al. (2020). Overcoming the energy gap law in near-infrared OLEDs by exciton–vibration decoupling. *Nat. Photonics* *14*, 570–577.
- ¹⁵ Tregnago, G., Steckler, T.T., Fenwick, O., Andersson, M.R., and Cacialli, F. (2015). Thia- and seleno-diazole containing polymers for near-infrared light-emitting diodes. *J. Mater. Chem. C* *3*, 2792–2797.
- ¹⁶ Fenwick, O., Sprafke, J.K., Binas, J., Kondratuk, D. V., Di Stasio, F., Anderson, H.L., and Cacialli, F. (2011). Linear and Cyclic Porphyrin Hexamers as Near-Infrared Emitters in Organic Light-Emitting Diodes. *Nano Lett.* *11*, 2451–2456.
- ¹⁷ Balijapalli, U., Nagata, R., Yamada, N., Nakanotani, H., Tanaka, M., D’Aléo, A., Placide, V., Mamada, M., Tsuchiya, Y., and Adachi, C. (2021). Highly Efficient Near-Infrared Electrofluorescence from a Thermally Activated Delayed Fluorescence Molecule. *Angew. Chemie Int. Ed.* *60*, 8477–8482.
- ¹⁸ Congrave, D.G., Drummond, B.H., Conaghan, P.J., Francis, H., Jones, S.T.E., Grey, C.P., Greenham, N.C., Credgington, D., and Bronstein, H. (2019). A Simple Molecular Design Strategy for Delayed Fluorescence toward 1000 nm. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* *141*, 18390–18394.
- ¹⁹ Chen, M., Perzon, E., Andersson, M.R., Marcinkevicius, S., Jönsson, S.K.M., Fahlman, M., and Berggren, M. (2004). 1 micron wavelength photo- and electroluminescence from a conjugated polymer. *Appl. Phys. Lett.* *84*, 3570–3572.